

Optimal Sensor Placement for Thermal Virtual Sensing in electronic systems using Augmented Kalman Filtering

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Abstract—The estimation of thermal parameters varying during the lifecycle of Electronic Components and Systems (ECS) is enabled by Digital Twins (DTs). The estimation performance depends on the number and utility of the chosen sensing locations. Moreover, large thermal gradients in ECS may cause misleading measurements resulting in wrong estimates. The presented Optimal Sensor Placement (OSP) algorithm considers parameter uncertainties thanks to the utilized DT framework composed of an Augmented Kalman Filter employing a parameter dependent thermal Reduced Order Model. Robustness in the sensor selection process is enforced by providing the OSP algorithm with the thermal gradients in the candidate sensing locations. A simulation study highlights the validity of the proposed methodology and opens to experimental validation.

Index Terms—augmented kalman filter, reduced order model, electronic components and systems, optimal sensor placement, thermal management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electronic Components and Systems (ECS) are subject to failures, mostly due to thermal issues, according to [1]. Real-time thermal monitoring is, therefore, fundamental to health monitoring, prediction of Remaining Useful Life (RUL), or thermal management. A solution was presented in [2] using a Digital Twin (DT) of an ECS, that is a Kalman Filter (KF) [3] employing a high-definition thermal numerical model.

Thanks to the parameter dependency [4], the model can be updated through estimation of the uncertain parameters by employing an Augmented Kalman Filter (AKF). However, the

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estimation performance depends on the location of the used sensors. Optimal sensor configurations are found by solving Optimal Sensor Placement (OSP) problems [5], [6], [7], where different cost functions can be considered.

In this study, an OSP algorithm is introduced tackling parameter uncertainty and sensor locations reliability depending on the thermal gradient present at the sensor location.

The presented methodology is numerically tested on a PCBA (printed circuit board assembly) - i.e. an electronic board with assembled components - also analyzing the outcome of the different cost functions used in the OSP problems.

II. FRAMEWORK

A. The parametric Reduced Order Model

The model is generated through Siemens Simcenter Flotherm [8], a simulation software for thermal analysis of electronic systems capable of exporting a Boundary Conditions Independent Reduced Order Model (BCI-ROM) [4], [9], allowing for real-time execution and preserving the dependency on the parameters of the boundary conditions, which are ambient temperature and Heat Transfer Coefficient (HTC). The BCI-ROM is a first-order system defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{T}_r &= f(T_r, S, p) \\ &= M_r^{-1} (-K_r(p)T_r + V_u S + S_r^a(p)), \\ T &= g(T_r) = V_o^T T_r, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

with input vector $S \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ containing the power dissipation, parameter vector $p \in \mathbb{R}^{n_p}$, temperature reduced state $T_r \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, and temperature field $T \in \mathbb{R}^{n_o}$. The reduced ambient source vector S_r^a models the heat exchange by thermal convection at the boundaries of the system. The matrices M_r and K_r represent the reduced thermal mass and the reduced thermal stiffness. The matrices V_u and V_o^T respectively project

the inputs onto the reduced space and the temperature reduced state onto the temperature field, and depend on the locations of inputs and sensors in the model.

Consistent with the AKF formulation, the following state-space formulation can be adopted for (1):

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x} &= f(x, u, p) = A(p)x + Bu + d(p), \\ y &= Cx.\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

B. The Augmented Kalman Filter

The estimation of unknown quantities of interest (QoI), like system inputs u and parameters p , is enabled by including them in the augmented state x_a as

$$x_a = \begin{bmatrix} x^\top & u^\top & p^\top \end{bmatrix}^\top = \begin{bmatrix} x^\top & q^\top \end{bmatrix}^\top. \quad (3)$$

Since no prior information about the augmented state variables q is available, their dynamics is modelled as a random walk by implementing a zeroth-order random-walk scheme in the system equations and by including process noises so that

$$\dot{x} = f_a(x_a) + w_a, \quad (4a)$$

$$y = C_a x_a + v_a, \quad (4b)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}f_a(x_a) &= \begin{bmatrix} f(x_a)^\top & 0_{1 \times n_q} \end{bmatrix}^\top, \quad w_a = \begin{bmatrix} w_x^\top & w_q^\top \end{bmatrix}^\top, \\ \begin{bmatrix} w_x \\ w_q \end{bmatrix} &\sim \mathbb{N} \left(\begin{bmatrix} 0_{n_x \times 1} \\ 0_{n_q \times 1} \end{bmatrix}, Q_a = \begin{bmatrix} Q_x & 0_{n_x \times n_q} \\ 0_{n_q \times n_x} & Q_q \end{bmatrix} \right), \\ C_a &= \begin{bmatrix} C & 0_{n_o \times n_q} \end{bmatrix}, \quad v_a \sim \mathbb{N}(0, R_a).\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

The estimation performance of the filter depends on the matrices Q_a and R_a . Generally, $R_a = \sigma_v^2 \times I_{n_o}$, with the variance σ_v^2 obtained from the sensor data sheet or by observing the noise in the measurement data. The tuning of Q_a is non-trivial and can be done with several methods, like L-curve [10], performance exploration [11], automated tuning [12], and adaptive tuning [13]. Usually Q_x is a zero matrix while Q_q is a diagonal matrix.

The filter is defined at the k -th iteration with the equations:

$$\hat{x}_{a,k+1}^- = f_{a,d}(\hat{x}_{a,k}^+), \quad (6a)$$

$$P_{a,k+1}^- = A_{a,d}(\hat{x}_{a,k+1}^-) P_{a,k}^+ A_{a,d}^\top(\hat{x}_{a,k+1}^-) + Q_{a,d}, \quad (6b)$$

$$K_{a,k+1} = P_{a,k+1}^- C_a^\top (C_a P_{a,k+1}^- C_a^\top + R_{a,d})^{-1}, \quad (6c)$$

$$\hat{x}_{a,k+1}^+ = \hat{x}_{a,k+1}^- + K_{a,k+1} (\tilde{y} - C_a \hat{x}_{a,k+1}^-), \quad (6d)$$

$$P_{a,k+1}^+ = (I - K_{a,k+1} C_a) P_{a,k+1}^-, \quad (6e)$$

where (6a) and (6b) define the prediction step, to calculate an a-priori state estimate $(\hat{x}_{a,k+1}^-, P_{a,k+1}^-)$, and (6c), (6d), and (6e) define the correction step, to calculate an a-posteriori state estimate $(\hat{x}_{a,k+1}^+, P_{a,k+1}^+)$. Discretization is executed, with a selected sampling time t_s , to obtain $f_{a,d}$, $A_{a,d}$ (by linearizing

$f_{a,d}$ in $\hat{x}_{a,k}^+$), $Q_{a,d}$, and $R_{a,d}$ [14]. The filter is initialized by setting the initial condition $(\hat{x}_{a,0}^+, P_{a,0}^+)$.

III. OPTIMAL SENSOR PLACEMENT

Several Optimal Sensor Placement (OSP) algorithms are found in literature [5], [6], [7]. A backward sequential sensor placement algorithm is introduced here, extending the one in [5] to tackle parameter uncertainty.

A. The algorithm

To select the optimal sensor locations, the unknowns estimate covariance matrix P_q is observed at steady-state. The matrix is found by solving the continuous-time Algebraic Riccati Equation (ARE)

$$A_a^\top P_a + P_a A_a - P_a C_a^\top R_a^{-1} C_a P_a + Q_a = 0 \quad (7)$$

and by projecting the state estimate covariance matrix P_a onto the QoI space through

$$P_q = H_q P_a H_q^\top, \quad H_q = \begin{bmatrix} 0_{n_q \times n_x} & I_{n_q} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

In case $f_a(x_a)$ is non-linear - i.e. by augmenting x_a with parameters p - the computation of the state matrix A_a requires the system's steady-state to be computed by setting q as the expected QoI.

The OSP algorithm works by removing one sensor at a time starting from the initial pool s_0 . The sensor to be removed is the one whose removal increases $c(P_q)$ the least. The choice of the set of sensors depends on the chosen cost function $c(P_q)$ in Table I, found in [6], [7], [15]. The 5th cost function of the table also uses P_q^+ , obtained by applying (8) to the result of (6e), with the ARE solution P_a in place of $P_{a,k+1}^-$.

Algorithm 1 OSP algorithm

- 1: Find x_a at steady-state, assuming q_0
 - 2: Compute $A_a(x_a)$
 - 3: **for** $k = 0 : n_o - 2$ **do**
 - 4: Obtain a set of sensors s_k
 - 5: Calculate $P_{a,k}$ for s_k and project it into $P_{q,k}$
 - 6: **for** $i = 1 : n_o - k$ **do**
 - 7: Obtain a set of sensors s_k^i from s_k ,
by removing the i -th sensor
 - 8: **if** System is observable **then**
 - 9: Calculate $P_{a,k}^i$ for s_k^i and project it into $P_{q,k}^i$
 - 10: **if** $c(P_q)$ requires normalization **then**
 - 11: Normalize diagonal elements of $P_{q,k}^i$
onto corresponding ones of $P_{q,0}$
 - 12: **end if**
 - 13: Evaluate $c(P_{q,k}^i)$
 - 14: **end if**
 - 15: **end for**
 - 16: Find the set of sensors s_k^i minimizing $c(P_q)$
 - 17: Update s_{k+1}
 - 18: **end for**
-

TABLE I: Table of cost functions

ID	Criterion	$c(P_q)$	Normalize P_q (Y/N)
A	A-optimality	$\text{Tr}(P_q)$	Y
D	D-optimality	$-\det(P_q^{-1})$	N
E	Entropy	$1/2 \cdot \ln((2\pi e)^{nq} \det(P_q))$	N
S	Sensitivity	$-\text{Tr}(P_q^{-1})$	Y
U	Utility	$\sum U_i; U_i = \frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{P_q^+}{P_q}\right)$	N

B. The mislocation noise

When tuning the measurement noise covariance matrix of the KF, measurements are generally assumed to be affected only by a zero-mean white Gaussian noise with a certain variance σ_v^2 . An additional source of uncertainty is however the match of the physical sensors locations with the corresponding locations in the numerical model. The uncertainty is evaluated numerically to provide the OSP algorithm with information about the reliability of the measurements depending on the sensor locations. The measurement error can be heavily affected by a sensor location mismatch at sensor locations presenting large thermal gradients.

The temperature error e_{T_i} of the i -th sensor depends on the model sensor location r_i and the spatial mislocation $e_{r,i}$ between the physical sensor location and r_i so that:

$$e_{T_i} = T(r_i + e_{r,i}, t) - T(r_i, t), \quad (9)$$

with $T(\cdot, t)$ the temperature field at time t . By computing the Taylor expansion of Eq. (9) around $e_{r,i} = 0$, and assuming the derivatives of the second order and higher are negligible, the relation $e_{T_i} = J_T(r_i, t)e_{r,i}$ holds, with J_T representing the thermal gradient.

Let us model e_T and e_r as temperature noise $v_T \sim \mathbb{N}(0, \sigma_T^2)$ and spatial mislocation noise $v_r \sim \mathbb{N}(0, R_r)$. Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{T,i}^2 &= \text{Var}(v_{T,i}) = E[v_{T,i}^2] - E[v_{T,i}]^2 = E[v_{T,i}^2] \\ &\simeq E[(J_T(r_i, t)v_{r,i})^2] = J_T(r_i, t)E[v_{r,i}^2]J_T^\top(r_i, t) \\ &= J_T(r_i, t)R_{r,i}J_T^\top(r_i, t) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

At steady-state, of interest for OSP,

$$\sigma_{T,i}^2 \simeq J_T(r_i)R_{r,i}J_T^\top(r_i). \quad (11)$$

By including $v_{T,i}$ in the i -th measurement equation of (4b), the resulting variance in the measurement noise covariance matrix $R_{a_{i,i}}$ is the sum of σ_v^2 and $\sigma_{T,i}^2$, which represents a weight in $R_{a_{i,i}}$.

IV. RESULTS

The considered setup consists of a $60\text{mm} \times 67\text{mm} \times 1.56\text{mm}$ test PCBA shown from the top in Fig. 1. The board, made out of FR4, features 6 silicon chips, several interface components, and a copper circuitry on top. Chip 1 is of size $(6.4 \times 6.4 \times 0.4)\text{mm}^3$ and chips 2-6 are of size

Fig. 1: Top view of the test PCBA. Chips are enumerated.

TABLE II: Thermal parameter values of the materials used in the model.

Material	Thermal conductivity [W/mK]	Density [kg/m ³]	Specific heat [J/kgK]
FR4	0.3	1200	880
Silicon	100	2330	700
Glue	0.5	2000	1000
Copper	385	8930	385

$(3.2 \times 3.2 \times 0.4)\text{mm}^3$. They are glued to the board through a $40\mu\text{m}$ thick die-attach. The circuitry is $17.6\mu\text{m}$ thick and is discretized in the software with thermal parameter values calculated based on the percentage of copper and FR4 in the corresponding volume region. The thermal parameter values are in Table II. The $(0.4 \times 0.4)\text{mm}^2$ light green patches on the board indicate 105 candidate locations for board sensors, selected so to fill all possible informative areas on the board while making sure avoiding overlapping or contact with chips or circuitry.

The HTC on top and on the lateral system boundaries is set at $10\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$ to model free air convection. The HTC at the bottom system boundary (bHTC) alternates from $470\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$ (nominal value) to $122\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$, to model dry attach to an aluminium cold plate depending on the air-gap thickness ($50\mu\text{m}$ or $200\mu\text{m}$). When powered on, chip 1 dissipates 0.6W and chips 2-6 dissipate 0.2W .

The nominal values q_{nom} are with bHTC at the nominal value and chips powered on. The reference values q_{ref} are defined considering bHTC alternating every 300s and chips switching on/off every 150s . At $t = 0\text{s}$, the system is at ambient temperature (293.15K) and $q_{ref,0} = q_{nom}$.

The filter requires the setting of $\hat{x}_{a,0}$, $P_{a,0}$, Q_a , R_a , and t_s . Since the system is known to be at ambient temperature at $t = 0s$, \hat{x}_0 represents this condition and $P_{x,0} = 0_{n_x \times n_x}$. No previous knowledge about q is provided. We choose to set $\hat{u}_0 = 0_{n_u \times 1}$, $\hat{p}_0 = 250W/m^2K$, a value in between those used in simulation, $P_{u,0} = 1W^2 \times I_{n_u}$ and $P_{p,0} = 2.5 \times 10^5 W^2 / (m^4 K^2)$. The variances on the main diagonal of Q_q are set to $\sigma_u^2 = 10^{-5} W^2$ for the unknown inputs and $\sigma_p^2 = 1W^2 / (m^4 K^2)$ for the unknown parameter in their corresponding locations. The variances on the main diagonal of R_a are set to $\sigma_v^2 = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} K^2$. Last, $t_s = 10^{-2} s$.

The variances $\sigma_{T,i}^2$ are added to the corresponding positions in matrix R_a for executing the OSP algorithm only. They are evaluated in the simulation software considering the thermal gradients in the model sensor locations, at steady-state with $q = q_{nom}$, and mislocation noises $v_{r,i}$ with diagonal covariance matrices $R_{r,i}$ assuming an uncertainty with standard deviation of $0.2mm$ per planar axis and no uncertainty on the perpendicular axis - i.e. contact with the board is assumed.

To highlight the OSP capabilities, a first case study is considered with 1 unknown QoI, the bHTC, while a second case study is considered with 7 unknown QoI, including the power dissipation of the 6 chips.

To check the robustness given by considering the mislocation noise in the OSP problem, the AKF is provided with an output matrix V_o^T depending on the reference sensor locations, in the center of the patches, while the simulated measurement data are from "physical" sensor locations, in one of the four corners of the patches. In particular, the worst case scenario is considered for every sensor location, that is, the chosen physical sensor location is the one with the largest $|e_{T_i}|$.

To evaluate the estimation performance, the Mean Normalized Residual Norm (MNRN) score is introduced as:

$$MNRN = mean(NRN) , NRN_k = \frac{\|\hat{q}_k^n - q_{ref,k}^n\|_2}{\|1_{n_q}\|_2} \quad (12)$$

with the superscript "n" indicating a normalization on q_{nom} . The score is evaluated through the bHTC period, 600s long.

A. First case study: 1 unknown QoI

The solution of the OSP problem for the case of 1 unknown QoI, the bHTC, shows no dependency of the order of sensor location selection on the adopted criterion. In Fig. 2 the evolution of the cost functions (normalized and inverted, if necessary, to be decreasing) during the OSP problem for different number of used sensors is reported. The criteria A, D, and S follow the same line, with no surprise as they depend on the same scalar and criterion E would follow the same evolution if it were not for the natural logarithm used in the formula. Criterion U evolves according to a different line, although the locations selection order does not change.

The optimal sensor locations selected by solving the OSP are indicated in Fig. 3. For the case of 1 unknown QoI, if *thermal gradients are considered* (TGC), L1 is the optimal location, while L4 is selected if *no thermal gradients are considered* (NTG). L4 is a more informative sensor location to

Fig. 2: Evolution of cost functions, normalized on the maximum value, for the number of used sensors, for 1 unknown.

Fig. 3: Optimal sensor locations selected by executing OSP in the two case studies.

estimate bHTC, but, due to the vicinity to chip 4, it is affected by a large thermal gradient and it is less reliable than L1.

The AKF estimation performance of bHTC using sensor L1 (TGC) and L4 (NTG) are reported in Fig. 4. The estimate obtained using TGC tracks the reference, while, especially during the first 300s, the estimation error is large and steady-state is not achieved when using NTG. Unrealistic negative value estimates, noticeable in Fig. 4, can be avoided by enforcing constraints in the KF [14]. The MNRN is 2.7% for AKF-TGC and 61.4% for AKF-NTG.

Fig. 4: AKF-TGC and AKF-NTG performance comparison for 1 unknown QoI.

Fig. 5: Evolution of cost functions, normalized on the maximum value, for the number of used sensors, for 7 unknowns.

Fig. 6: MNRN for the 80 sensor configurations tested.

B. Second case study: 7 unknown QoI

The solution of the OSP problem for the case of 7 unknown QoI, the bHTC and the power dissipation of the 6 chips, shows a dependency of the order of sensor locations selection on the adopted criterion. However, the selection order is the same for criteria D and E (see Table I), because both of them rely on the determinant of P_q or its inverse. In the following, the sensor selection obtained with these criteria will be referred to as the criterion D sensor selection.

In Fig. 5 the evolutions of the cost functions for the different criteria for the case of 7 unknown QoI are reported, similarly to Fig. 2. Cost functions evolve differently in this case, indicating different orders of sensor locations selection.

Combining the 4 optimality criteria with the option of thermal gradients to solve the OSP, 8 orders of sensor locations selection are obtained. For each order, 10 sensor configurations are tested ranging from 7 (the minimum) to 16 used sensors, for a total of 80 sensor configurations. The MNRN for each sensor configuration is represented in Fig. 6, keeping in mind the mislocation of the worst case scenario is considered. The TGC sensor configurations outperform the NTG ones in 28 out of 40 comparisons (70%). The MNRN is above 40% when using 7 sensors (optimal minimal configuration) and it sharply drops down to values around 20% at 8 sensors (S criterion), 9 sensors (D and U criteria), and 10 sensors (A criterion) to eventually reach values around 15% on average for the investigated sensor configurations with 15 and 16 sensors. Hence, the MNRN seems to evolve similarly for all criteria,

Fig. 7: MNRN cumulative distributions for 100 TGC and NTG configurations of random sensor mislocations.

highlighting that no particular advantage is obtained by using a specific criterion for OSP.

The optimal minimal sensor locations selected by solving the OSP for 7 unknown QoI are indicated in Fig. 3. The optimal minimal sensor configurations include all locations but L6, for TGC, and but L1, for NTG. Both of them are independent on the adopted criterion. The similarity of the two configurations indicates that the mislocation noise term is outweighed by the informativeness of the selected locations for input estimation. In particular, the NTG configuration outperforms the TGC one. Although contradictory, we point out that only one mislocation case scenario is considered, which is therefore not statistically relevant. To better represent the estimation performance with 7 sensors, 100 configurations of random sensor mislocations (50 for TGC and 50 for NTG) were generated using measurement data from random locations in the sensor patches. The MNRN is evaluated for each configuration. The MNRN cumulative distributions for TGC and NTG configurations are compared in Fig. 7. NTG configurations have minimum, average, and maximum MNRN respectively of 5.8%, 14.5%, and 27.0% whilst TGC configurations respectively score 7.4%, 13.4%, and 34.3%. Although, NTG configurations score better minimum and maximum MNRNs, TGC configurations score a better average MNRN and, in general, score lower values than NTG ones. Average, minimum, and maximum estimation performance of the 7 unknown QoI using TGC are shown, with the references, in Fig. 8.

V. CONCLUSION

This work proposes a DT framework using an AKF employing a ROM of an ECS thermal model to obtain real-time thermal measurements from virtual sensors - i.e. estimated temperatures - by estimating unknown system QoI. An OSP algorithm dealing with unknown system inputs (linear dependence) and parameters (non-linear dependence) is proposed that can also consider thermal gradients present in the candidate sensor locations to weight their reliability while solving the sensor placement problem.

The validity of the methodology is assessed in a simulated environment on a PCBA model by analyzing the estimation

Fig. 8: Performance comparison of AKF with minimum, average, and maximum MNRN for 7 unknown QoI using TGC set.

performance of the system unknown QoI assuming measurement data are from locations misplaced from those declared in the model employed in the filter. Several sensor configurations are tested obtained for different optimality criteria adopted while solving the OSP. Evidence highlighted that more reliable sensor locations are selected if considering thermal gradients with the introduced mislocation noise term. Also, no particular advantage in terms of estimation performance is obtained by adopting a specific cost function over the others. However, it must be noted that criterion A does not entail determinant calculation, matrix inversion, or estimate covariance update necessary for the other criteria and hence is the criterion with the lowest computational cost.

Two case studies are investigated assuming either 1 unknown QoI, the HTC at the bottom of the system (bHTC), or 7 unknown QoI, including the power dissipation of the 6 chips. In the first case, the DT achieved a 2.7% MNRN of the parameter estimate in the worst case scenario using the optimal minimal TGC sensor configuration. In the second case, the DT achieved average values of 13.4% and 14.5% MNRN, respectively for TGC and NTG optimal minimal sensor configurations, on one hand stressing the estimation

reliability improvement by considering the thermal gradients in the sensor selection problem, but on the other hand highlighting the increased challenge when power dissipation estimation for this kind of system is required.

The presented work numerically validates the proposed methodology and paves the way for validation against experimental measurements. The obtained estimation performance indicates that the calibration of the model sensor locations is necessary after instrumenting the system if input estimation is required, or that other informative sensor locations which are less affected by thermal gradients, like at the bottom of the board right behind the chips, should be considered.

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